

cessda

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

Annual Report 2018

Foreword

It is a privilege to work at CESSDA. When I started in 2017, I already knew that there would be gemstones to discover in working for a social data infrastructure. Some had to be polished first and in 2018 we could go live with the CESSDA Data Catalogue, successfully ensure our European coverage, launch a new website and provide excellent training. More gems will come over the next few years too.

Social data is increasing in relevance for the sciences and for tackling the grand societal challenges. There are several professionally designed European and global data collections that are used by hundreds of thousands of users (SHARE, ESS, GGP, EVS, WageIndicator), and CESSDA Service Providers play an important role in archiving and making these data available. In addition to survey data, new types of data have appeared on the horizon (social media,

registries) as well as a growing need to link different data, also from other disciplines (e.g. geography and health). To provide data as a service will be our challenge, especially as a significant portion of social data requires a secured environment.

Looking ahead, I can see CESSDA becoming more mature both as a consortium and as an ERIC¹. We share expertise and best practice cases with other ERICs in the ERIC Forum. As a consortium, the Main Office is now in shape, and the coordination of Service Providers' activities improved. The Working Groups are chaired and staffed by experts from the Service Providers. This growth is no reason to stop pushing ahead. We can develop and provide even better professional services and deepen our working cooperation with other disciplines, with our research communities and with e-infrastructures.

CESSDA has some interesting challenges ahead. In early 2019, we became the coordinator of the EOSC-cluster project SSHOC, the social sciences & humanities open cloud. We are exploring new directions, or as Captain Kirk from the starship Enterprise stated: "to boldly go where no one has gone before". This is not only for astronauts or astronomers, but also goes for social sciences. We face interesting times ahead and CESSDA wants to be part of it!

Sincerely,

Ron Dekker, Director

¹ European Research Infrastructure Consortium

Foreword

CESSDA has gone through several transformations since its original foundation as a membership organisation of social science data archives in 1976. For many people who think that data-driven research is something of the last decade or so, it may come as a surprise that social scientists were among the very first to set up repositories for data sharing and preservation. Actually, the first data archives date back to the 1960s, the era of punch cards, magnetic tapes and mainframe computers. It is hard to imagine that at that time data was shared by sending a request by traditional mail, and that tapes were also sent to interested users as mail packages.

It was a bold, and by no means easy, step to embark on the course of becoming a pan-European Scientific Research Infrastructure. This first step was taken in 2006, when CESSDA was listed in the first ESFRI Roadmap. In 2013 it was founded as a European research infrastructure, and in 2017 it acquired the official ERIC status. The whole process took more than ten years, a decade in which a data explosion was taking place.

The past few years, and 2018 in particular, were characterised by several interrelated trends, in which CESSDA participated or which it stimulated. Social scientists set standards for data exchange that long preceded the FAIR Data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) and developed good practices for research data management long before research funders and other organisations started to require data management plans. One of CESSDA successes of 2018 was the bringing together of expertise in this area in the form of an online expert guide for data management. Although a common European catalogue already existed in the times of the “old CESSDA”, last year it was thoroughly renewed and published, thus providing an overview of thousands of datasets available from Service Providers across Europe, with links to access the data.

Social science survey research is also changing. The use of public registration data, new data collection techniques via the internet, big data from social media, provide new possibilities for social analysis. Linking data from a multitude of data

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sources using semantic technologies has opened up opportunities that were unheard of until a few years ago. But there are also worries connected to these possibilities, for instance about the abuse of interconnected data, both by big companies and by big government. 2018 was the year that the General Data Protection Regulation came into force, a European law that the CESSDA Service Providers are dealing with in their data provision.

Artificial intelligence based on deep learning in combination with facial recognition may result in undesired social profiling and political manipulation. These are aspects that social scientists should not neglect. At the same time, increasing refusal rates to participate in surveys by the public creates biases in survey results. The costs of carrying out a complete interview have exploded. Perhaps that in the near future listening speech assistants will take over the role of the door-to-door interviewer, which will potentially bring enormous savings.

There will always be a hunger to know how the opinions and behaviours of people and social groups change, therefore it will remain necessary to collect data about what people think and do, and to compare that with how this was in the past. Therefore, the services of social science data archives will remain indispensable.

Of course, data services similar to those of CESSDA members are also being developed in other domains. More than ever it is clear that we have common interests and that we can learn from each

other. This is also why CESSDA actively participates in all kinds of interdisciplinary or multidisciplinary data endeavours, first of all with other players in the Humanities and Social Sciences, and also by preparing for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). CESSDA is aware of the fact that society and the economy require fair, transparent and open science, while at the same time recognising that the privacy of respondents in data sets needs to be protected. CESSDA itself has transformed over the past few years into a mature and open European data organisation.

Sincerely,

Peter Doorn, Chair of the GA (and director of DANS, the Netherlands)

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Highlights

CESSDA was listed as an ESFRI Landmark in the field of Social & Cultural Innovation in the last two ESFRI Roadmaps, in 2016 and [2018](#). The CESSDA Strategy 2018-2022 was published in June, which sets out the priority areas and gives the direction of future work for the consortium.

The CESSDA Main Office in Bergen has grown over the last two years, with two new staff members starting in 2017 and four in 2018. The CESSDA Technical Working Group leader from UK Data Service also started a new role as CESSDA Platform Delivery Director working

remotely. This was crucial for the delivery of the CESSDA Data Catalogue, which was launched in November 2018.

During the course of 2018, several countries were in the pipeline for membership. The General Assembly accepted Serbia's bid to join during its meeting on 22 November 2018, paving the way for formal membership in early 2019. Two events aimed at widening CESSDA's European coverage were organised, first in Milan in June and then in Belgrade in November.

CESSDA's listing in the ESFRI roadmap 2018

A large scale, integrated and sustainable platform for data services to the social sciences

NORWAY

CESSDA ERIC

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

TYPE distributed

LEGAL STATUS ERIC, 2017

POLITICAL SUPPORT
lead country: NO
member countries: AT, BE, CZ, DE, DK, EL, FI, FR, HU, NL, PT, SE, SI, SK, UK
***observer:** CH
The full list of research institutions involved must be found in the website of the RI

ROADMAP ENTRY 2006

TIMELINE

ESTIMATED COSTS
capital value: 117 M€
design: 4 M€
preparation: 2.7 M€
construction: 78 M€
operation: 39 M€/year

HEADQUARTERS
CESSDA ERIC
Bergen, Norway

WEBSITE
www.cessda.eu

Highlights

In terms of outreach, CESSDA joined the EOSC Executive Board in November 2018, which is tasked with providing advice and support on the strategy, implementation, monitoring and reporting of the EOSC. CESSDA also joined the European Alliance for Social Sciences and Humanities (EASSH), which promotes research in social sciences and humanities, attending its General Assembly meeting in November in Vienna. The Research Data Alliance's 12th Plenary meeting took place in Botswana on 5-8 November 2018, as part of International Data Week and CESSDA was one of the founders of a new RDA Interest Group on Social Science Research Data.

International Data Week 2018, Botswana

The very first "train the trainers" workshop took place in Ljubljana, hosted by the Slovenian Service Provider ADP. CESSDA organised a Love Data Management webinar during Love Data Week in February, took part in the EOSC Summit 2018, and was represented in the European Commission Expert Group on FAIR Data by Scientific Advisory Board member Simon Hodson from CODATA. The

annual CESSDA Expert Seminar covered CESSDA's technical Infrastructure and cloud computing, and examined the development, testing and deployment of CESSDA Tools and Services.

CESSDA also renewed its corporate identity in 2018 and professionalised its communication channels (a new logo, website, leaflet, rebranded and improved social media channels). The CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide was updated and became the most visited part of the website. CESSDA started a new series of interviews with high-level stakeholders. The first interview was carried out with Robert-Jan Smits, then open access envoy of the European Commission.

Over half of CESSDA Service Providers (SPs) were certified data repositories by the end of 2018, having obtained or renewed their CoreTrustSeal certifications. CESSDA SPs began the implementation work following from the CESSDA Persistent Identifier Policy. They also turned their attention to developing Extended Best Practice Guidelines on specific topics related to the FAIR Data principles.

User survey results from the Finnish SP FSD revealed high user satisfaction and the Swiss SP FORS celebrated its tenth anniversary. Norwegian SP NSD and Statistics Norway launched the microdata.no project, which aims to simplify secured access to Statistics Norway's register data.

Introduction

CESSDA provides large-scale, integrated and sustainable data services to the social sciences. It brings together social science data archives across Europe, with the aim of promoting the results of social science research and supporting national and international research and cooperation.

The [CESSDA Strategy 2018-2022](#) has four pillars:

1. Building on TRUST
2. Renown for TRAINING
3. Proficient in TECHNOLOGY
4. User-friendly TOOLS & SERVICES.

CESSDA builds trust in social science research by ensuring its quality and that it is available for future research. By acquiring the status of a trust repository, CESSDA Service Providers demonstrate their reliability to researchers as well as national and international research funders.

CESSDA supports continuous learning and training of its Service Providers' staff and the social science user community. The areas covered include research data management, data discovery and reuse, digital preservation and data archiving, as well as CESSDA tools and services.

Technology refers to the technical infrastructure behind CESSDA that ensures a stable and up-to-date backbone for our products and services, making it simple and easy to both deposit and access data.

Tools & Services focus on the demands by researchers and realise tools for seamless access to research data and easy deposit and archiving of data.

Staff at CESSDA and its Service Providers in 2018

Country	Organisation	Staff in CESSDA activities
Main Office	CESSDA	10
AT	AUSSDA	9
BE	SOHDA	2
CH	FORS	13
CZ	CSDA	8
DE	GESIS	88
DK	DDA	13
FI	FSD	26
FR	PROGEDO	7
UK	UKDA	30
GR	So.Da.Net	6
HU	TARKI	4
NL	DANS	55
NO	NSD	20
PT	APIS	5
SE	SND	16
SK	SASD	2
SI	ADP	5

The CESSDA Consortium 2018

Activities and results

Training activities

Training Roadmap

The Training Working Group produced a roadmap of their objectives for the period 2019 - 2022. The Roadmap and its future updates will provide a longer perspective to complement funding applications for annual working group plans and project proposals.

The CESSDA Training Group supports CESSDA's overall mission and vision by raising awareness about Open Science and the FAIR Data principles, as well as by increasing the data skills of researchers. This is done through providing training courses and educational materials for trainers working in CESSDA Service Providers and in partner organisations, for other data professionals and for researchers in the social sciences and humanities.

The Training Group aims to improve the data sharing culture, starting with data management skills and through promoting the use of secondary data, which is done by improving data discovery skills. The Group works closely with national, European and global actors, such as OpenAIRE, the Research Data Alliance, DDI-metadata and other European Open Science Cloud projects, and is helping to build a community of practice in the field of training.

CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide

One of the main objectives of the Training Group during 2018 was to create new training resources in data discovery. These resources are created to directly support researchers, by providing them with international research data expertise.

The newly developed training materials on data discovery were piloted during workshops, summer schools and webinars. The materials were enhanced, based on user feedback, and incorporated into the online training guide.

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DMEG Data Management
Expert Guide

The CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide was, amongst others, presented at

- » RDA Plenary, Berlin, March
- » Workshop Legal and Ethical Aspect of Research Data, Ljubljana, April
- » Platform for Survey Research, Rotterdam, May
- » IASSIST Conference, Montreal, May
- » How to get the maximum from research data - Workshop, Tartu, May
- » CESSDA Widening Meeting, Milan, June
- » Open Science for SSH Researchers, Net4Society webinar, June
- » CESSDA Widening Meeting, Belgrade, November

Activities and results

[The CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide](#) is designed to support social science researchers. It had six chapters upon its launch in December 2017 (Plan, Organise & Document, Process, Store, Protect and Archive & Publish).

At the end of 2018, the seventh chapter on finding and accessing data in Europe named “Discover” was added.

The DMEG was heavily promoted among CESSDA partners at the beginning of the year, after its initial launch, and quickly became the most visited part of the CESSDA website. A poster was created and showed at the [Digital Infrastructures for research](#) event in Lisbon on 9-11 October 2018.

CESSDA Training has a dedicated section on the new version of the CESSDA website launched in November 2018, as well as increased visibility from the homepage and in the navigation. Together with the CESSDA Data Catalogue, Tools & Services, Training stands out as a main service offered by CESSDA.

A new feature of the CESSDA training website is the training calendar, which shows events organised by the group. An online form will become available in the course of 2019, so that group members can become more active in promoting their events on the CESSDA website. A printable version of the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide is also planned for 2019.

² Presentations and recordings are available on the CESSDA Training website: <https://www.cessda.eu/Training/Training-Resources/Research-Data-Management>

Webinars and workshops

A “Love Data Management” webinar took place on 16 February 2018 during the Love Data Week, providing an overview of the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide and how to navigate it². A special focus was given to data management planning and key legal and ethical considerations in creating shareable data.

The data discovery team held two webinars in 2018 dedicated to specific research groups. The

Activities and results

first webinar, entitled “Data in Europe: Migration” attracted 73 participants and took place in May and the second one on “Poverty” (with 64 participants) took place in November³. In May, a workshop entitled “Exploring Data in Europe – with a Focus on European Attitudes and Values” took place in Prague, Czech Republic (23 participants)⁴. The first part of the workshop was dedicated to the general topic of discovering data in CESSDA archives, and the second part to studies on attitudes and values. Developed materials were used at several summer schools and subsequently updated.

Summer Schools in 2018

- » Essex Summer School (12 July 2018) - 17 participants
<http://essexsummerschool.com/>
- » Ljubljana Doctoral Summer School (18 July 2018) - 10 participants
<https://www.google.com/url?q=http://www.ef.uni-lj.si/>
- » Global School in Empirical Research Methods – GSERM , Ljubljana (22 and 29 August 2018) – 3 and 11 participants
<https://www.gsrm.ch/ljubljana/>
- » GESIS summer school (20-21 August 2018) - 4 participants
<https://www.gesis.org/en/services/events/gesis-training/summer-school/>

In addition, the project delivered a train the trainers workshop in April in Ljubljana, for data professionals working in less mature SPs or for

new staff as well as staff from CESSDA partners. The workshop addressed how to use the DMEG in training courses. Slides from webinars and other workshop materials are available for trainers under a CC-BY-SA license.

The Training Group also supported new trainers in delivering training courses for researchers at their locations. Three such events took place in 2018, presenting the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide, namely in Kausa, Lithuania, organised by CESSDA partner SP LiDA, in Copenhagen, Denmark, organized by the Danish SP DNA and in The Hague, Netherlands, organised by the Dutch SP DANS.

We plan to provide expert level training and training materials, covering the entire OAIS model, which can be used by trainers from CESSDA SPs as well as researchers depositing and using survey data. The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals shall be used as a framework for training on the use of data.

Train-the-trainers workshop, Ljubljana, April 2018

³ Presentations and recordings are available on CESSDA Training website: <https://www.cessda.eu/Training/Training-Resources/Data-Discovery-and-Reuse>

⁴ The presentations are published here: <https://www.cessda.eu/Consortium/Communication/Events/CESSDA-Workshop-Exploring-Data-in-Europe-with-a-Focus-on-European-Attitudes-and-Values>

Activities and results

Trust activities

The internationally accepted CoreTrustSeal is mandatory for all Service Providers. CESSDA SPs must be perceived as trusted bodies by stakeholders including universities, national statistical offices, funders and researchers. Six organisations with experience in Trustworthy Digital Repositories and the CoreTrust Seal participate in the Trust Group.

Supporting Service Providers

During 2018 a special case was investigated: a partnership model with four different organisations within one Service Provider. The SP prepared one self-assessment and four separate peer reviews related to the partners which make up the French CESSDA SP PRODEGO were completed. Trust Group members' feedback was delivered as a coordinated response including guidance for revisions during 2019. This PRODEGO review presents an example of partnership models which are acknowledged as a growing use case and future challenge by the CoreTrustSeal Board.

In the case of PROGEDO, the standard support process was followed: the SP prepares a self-assessment against the CoreTrustSeal and submits it to the Trust Group. This reduces the burden on the (voluntary) CoreTrustSeal

reviewers while increasing the overall quality and consistency of CESSDA submissions through internal cooperation and knowledge exchange. As part of the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project, members of the Trust Group will join partners from across the SSH Infrastructures to extend this approach⁵.

Certification Progress

At the beginning of 2018, two SPs had achieved certification against the CoreTrustSeal (2017-2019 version of the Requirements).

During 2018, a further five SPs and one CESSDA partner gained the CoreTrustSeal:

DANS: Electronic Archiving SYstem (EASY)
Norwegian NSD's Research Data Archive
Swedish National Data Service
Czech Social Science Data Archive (CSDA)
German GESIS Data Archive for the Social Sciences
Irish Social Science Data Archive (ISSDA, CESSDA Partner)

As a distributed research infrastructure seeking to strengthen and widen its membership, it is important that nine of the seventeen CESSDA Service Providers were certified in 2018⁶.

5 The SSHOC project started in 2019 and runs until 2022: <https://www.cessda.eu/About/Projects/Current-projects/SSHOC>

6 For a full overview, see "[Trust monitoring status - end of year 2018](#)" in annex.

Activities and results

Targeted events on key topics

Previous Trust Group events have focused on an overview of the CoreTrustSeal requirements and consideration of how they apply to CESSDA members. The first targeted event was a technically-focused trust workshop, which took place in Ljubljana on 27 September 2018. In-depth discussion on Technical Infrastructure and information security followed a technical overview session. The day concluded with an integrated view of technical issues across all sixteen requirements.

Maja Dolinar (ADP) delivered workshop outcomes via a poster at the International Data Week 2018 (IDW 2018) on 5-8 November 2018 in Gaborone, Botswana.

The same methodology was followed for a Trust workshop co-located with the [EDDI2018 Conference](#) (4-5 December 2018) in Berlin.

As we seek to align best practices and increase interoperability (e.g. EOSC) and standardisation (CoreTrustSeal and FAIR data), the wider technical and metadata landscape becomes more critical.

Current Activity & Future Plans

CESSDA repositories are keen to adopt best practice and apply the latest standards. The Trust Group will continue to support applications, renewals and those organisations not yet in a position to apply. The CoreTrustSeal will be reviewed and potentially revised during 2019 and the Trust Group will contribute and monitor potential impact.

From 2019 the Trust Group will remain flexible in response to changes in the certification status and maturity of CESSDA SPs/partners, and to the wider European science environment including by:

- » focussing more on individual trust requirements, their implications and the evidence needed to support them;
- » analysis to monitor the landscape of trust and trust-related issues beyond CESSDA.

Activities and results

Tools & Services activities

The Tools & Services Working Group was established in late 2017 and thus year 2018 was the first operational year of the Group. The group was set up with the aim of representing users and to help decide what needs to be developed based on the interests of this group. The group held eleven meetings in 2018, of which nine were virtual and two face-to-face meetings in connection with other meetings.

Tools and Services Roadmap

The Tools & Services Working Group produced a roadmap of their objectives for the period 2019 - 2022. The vision is to offer a platform with tools and services to both data producers and data users, and to be part of the European Open Science Cloud.

The CESSDA services aimed at users are based on good quality metadata and data. In the next four years, Service Providers will need to take major steps to provide metadata compatible with the CESSDA metadata model (CMM). From 2019, the Tools & Services Working Group will focus on recognising collaboration opportunities, sharing knowledge, and advancing initiatives that aim at improved data discovery.

The objectives are pursued via the activities of the Tools and Services Working Group, Work Plan projects, EU-funded and other projects,

the Technical Working Group and CESSDA Main Office staff.

Work Plan Projects in 2018

CESSDA Metadata Management Phase 2

The outputs from this project included the CESSDA Metadata Model, Controlled Vocabularies, User Guide, Management and Maintenance Plan and Impact Analysis. The outputs ensure that all Service Providers as well as CESSDA's services have the same understanding of metadata, and that the tools and services developed by or for CESSDA are interoperable when it comes to metadata.

DataverseEU

Dataverse is an open source tool for (self) archiving, developed by Harvard University (<https://dataverse.org/>). The project developed a data repository solution targeted especially at aspiring and new Service Providers. New functionalities include the possibility of having multiple languages, and support of specific metadata. These new functionalities are shared with the global Dataverse community and were integrated in Dataverse. A development version has been published (<https://dataverse-dev.cessda.eu/>), and work on DataverseEU continues in the SSHOC project.

Activities and results

Euro Question Bank

The Euro Question Bank project develops a cross-national question bank with a central search facility across all CESSDA's survey holdings to display survey questions in different languages. In 2018, the metadata schema was finished, a test version of the user interface with main functionalities developed, and work on backend components continued. The service is expected to go online in 2019.

CESSDA Vocabulary Service

The CESSDA Vocabulary Service is a Controlled Vocabulary curation tool that allows multiple agencies (CESSDA ERIC, DDI Alliance, Service Providers) to create, edit and manage their own CV content. All CVs are available in English, and many are available in other languages. A public version is due early 2019.

Activities and results

Technical activities

CESSDA Data Catalogue

The [CESSDA Data Catalogue](#) went live at the beginning of November 2018. It does not hold any data itself, or provide direct access to data, but automatically and periodically harvests metadata from Service Providers and other sources. Fully automated harvesting is crucial to ensure that the CESSDA Data Catalogue content is up to date. At the time of writing circa 27,000 study records are available: 19,000 in English and 8,000 in the other languages of the CESSDA community⁷.

⁷ For more insight into the new CESSDA Data Catalogue, see the presentation at EDDI18 - <https://zenodo.org/record/2530106#XJiIRSj7SUk>

CESSDA Expert Seminar

The CESSDA Expert Seminar 2018 ([CES2018](#)) took place in Ljubljana in September 2018, chaired by John Shepherdson, CESSDA Platform Delivery Director and leader of the CESSDA Technical Working Group.

Targeting the software development community within CESSDA Service Providers and Observers, CES2018 was designed for a maximum of 30 participants. The goals were raising common technical standards within CESSDA, enhancing the skills of the CESSDA software development community and training the trainers within CESSDA Training with regard to preparing and delivering content for a technical audience.

Based on feedback from the expert seminar, a one-day event was organised to present and explain the IT-tools that are being used by CESSDA: Jenkins, Docker, Kubernetes, Helm and Tiller. The intended audience was CESSDA Service Provider staff working on the implementation of CESSDA Tools and Services and of their own back office systems. There were 12 attendees. Also, a Developers' Workshop took place as an [EDDI18 side event](#) in Berlin on 6 December 2018.

Activities and results

Technical Roadmap

The CESSDA Technical Working Group produced a roadmap of their objectives for the period 2019 - 2022. The vision is to provide a distributed and sustainable research infrastructure.

These objectives are to ensure CESSDA has a trusted platform for researchers which provides tools and services to curate, publish and reuse research data. The vision is published by the Technical Working Group, and the objectives are pursued via the activities of the Technical Working Group, CESSDA Main Office technical staff and the Technical Framework project.

Technical Framework project

This project focused on the operational aspects of the technical infrastructure. It also oversaw the development and deployment of the Data Catalogue and the initial deployment of the Vocabulary Service.

The project produced the following public deliverables:

- » CESSDA Technical Architecture
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2631328>
- » CESSDA Software Maturity Levels
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2614050>
- » CESSDA ERIC User Experience Guide
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2631263>

Activities and results

Widening activities

The CESSDA Strategy 2018-2022 highlighted the need to increase efforts in widening our European coverage over the coming years. In 2018, CESSDA actively built on the achievements of the CESSDA Strengthening and Widening project during the 2015-2017 period.

The continued widening activities were organised in the framework of the annual CESSDA Work Plan and supported by additional CESSDA Main Office initiatives. The Widening Group was made up of staff from six CESSDA Service Providers in 2018: CSDA, FORS, ADP, TARKI, DANS, and SND.

The main objectives were:

- » to maintain and foster the network of CESSDA Partners, i.e., the network of non-member, European SPs and emerging archiving activities working with CESSDA;

- » to share existing CESSDA support services, tools and knowledge among CESSDA Partners;
- » to maintain and further develop strategic knowledge about existing non-member Service Providers and proto-archiving activities;
- » to increase CESSDA's visibility in non-member countries.

Widening events in 2018

The two widening events organised by CESSDA in 2018 were targeted at representatives from ministries, research councils and Service Providers of potential new member countries. They aimed to demonstrate the benefits of joining CESSDA. A main focus of the events was sharing practical information on building CESSDA-compliant data services, as well as CESSDA technologies, tools, standards, and training opportunities. Moreover, the events provided a platform for panel discussions on available resources, needs, and existing gaps.

1st CESSDA Widening Meeting 2018, Milan, 5-6 June

Activities and results

The first CESSDA Widening Meeting 2018 was held in [Milan, Italy, on 5-6 June 2018](#). It was hosted by the Interdepartmental Centre UniData – Bicocca Archive at the Università degli Studi di Milano-Bicocca. In total 48 representatives from 23 European countries attended the meeting. A distinguished guest, Jan Hrušák, then ESFRI Vice-Chair also participated⁸.

The second CESSDA Widening Meeting 2018 was held in [Belgrade, Serbia, on 14-15 November 2018](#). It was hosted by the Institute of Economic Sciences in Belgrade. 43 participants from 24 different European countries took part in the meeting as well as representatives of two collaborating research infrastructures, OpenAIRE and DARIAH-EU.

Developments in non-member countries

The first monitoring report on CESSDA non-member countries was published within the CESSDA SaW project in 2017. In 2018, this information was updated and the monitoring exercise was upgraded to allow continuous monitoring. A total of 22 non-member countries in the European Research Area were approached in 2018 and semi-structured interviews were carried out. This resulted in country reports and summaries, which can be used by CESSDA for

2nd CESSDA Widening Meeting 2018, Belgrade, 14-15 November

assessing the potential of these countries for joining CESSDA in the future. The results are also relevant for country data professionals, social science researchers and decision makers, as they demonstrate continuous efforts to build a sustainable data service and identify the current obstacles that need to be addressed collectively.

The reports and other results produced by the widening group have so far primarily been shared within CESSDA and with the network of CESSDA Partners. These findings should become available for a wider audience in the course of 2019.

⁸ More information is available here: <https://www.cessda.eu/widening2018/>

Activities and results

Communications

CESSDA prioritised its communications work in 2018, by developing a new graphic profile, modernising its website and making it more user-friendly and by delivering a communication and dissemination strategy to guide future work.

The new CESSDA website went online in November, with a more user-friendly design and with products and services being made easily accessible to the specific user groups to which they are addressed (data users, data producers, Service Providers and members). Training received a dedicated online space with its own calendar. The focus was on making the main tools and services easily available: CESSDA Data Catalogue & Training website. The new tools & services section directs users to existing tools based on self categorising by website viewers.

A communication and dissemination strategy was developed and implemented, which gave direction to future communication work. Monthly communication group virtual meetings were organised by the Senior Communication Officer and the communication staff of the Service Providers. These helped ensure the flow of internal information between CESSDA MO, the SPs and between the SPs, and allowed for engagement and the sharing of best practices.

Online activity

Website visits

File downloads

Twitter impressions

Top visitor countries

Top website sections

Activities and results

European Union funded projects

Synergies for Europe's Research Infrastructures in the Social Sciences (SERISS)

Duration: 01.07.2015.-30.08.2019

Funded by: European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

For the past three years the project Synergies for Europe's Research Infrastructures in the Social Sciences (SERISS) has been bringing together Europe's leading social science research infrastructures to address key challenges in cross-national research, and to break down barriers between infrastructures, embracing the future of social research.

In 2018, the SERISS team in CESSDA was responsible for several crucial deliverables which helped the project successfully enter into its final year. The CESSDA team included the following CESSDA Service Providers: UK Data Service (United Kingdom), ADP (Slovenia), FORS (Switzerland), CSDA (Czech Republic), GESIS (Germany), and NSD (Norway).

The CESSDA team focused on issues such as indexing terms in the data life cycle, cross-national and longitudinal data harmonisation in an online library, working with new forms of data, data versioning and metadata and data linkage.

A workshop on "Legal and ethical issues of combining survey data with new forms of data" took place on 19 June 2018 at CITY, University of London. This looked at the challenges and solutions for linking survey data with new forms of data in light of the new General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). It brought together researchers, survey practitioners and other stakeholders (representatives from data archives, national statistics institutes, social media platforms) involved in data collection, data preservation and data linkage. In total 32 participants attended this interactive workshop.

Academic and scientific ecosystems are rapidly evolving, and data archives face a number of challenges. For example, the delay which exists between the emergence of new data and technology and their deposit in repositories generates further risk. The CESSDA team provided an overview of appraisal and selection practices for novel forms of data, as well as possible future approaches to addressing them.

Activities and results

European Research Infrastructures in the International Landscape (RISCAPE)

Duration: 01.01.2017 - 31.12.2019

Funded by: European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

The RISCAPE project will produce a landscape analysis and a comprehensive overview of what kind of major research facilities exist worldwide and the positioning of European facilities. The report to be delivered by the project will have a direct and beneficial effect on the European Union's Research Infrastructure policy.

In order to achieve this goal, the project consortium has established a stakeholder panel representing the main user groups of the report, including representatives from ESFRI, OECD and EU Member State funding agencies, to ensure the usability of the report.

9 <http://www.interreg-danube.eu/>

CESSDA is participating in the thematic work package that deals with the social sciences landscape. CESSDA team includes the CESSDA Main Office and UK Data Service. In 2018, an action plan was created to provide an overview of social science research infrastructures in the European Research Area. The plan identified key relevant initiatives in the international research infrastructure ecosystem. In 2019 several interviews are planned to cover the social science landscape and for the report to be finalised by the end of 2019.

European Commission projects in the pipeline

CESSDA was involved in the preparation of several project proposals in the course of 2018:

- » Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud - SSHOC under the call INFRAEOSC-04-2018 (as coordinator)
- » ERIC Forum Implementation proposal under the call INFRASUPP-01-2018-2019 (as project beneficiary).

Both project proposals were submitted by the end of March 2018 and granted funding the same year. The scheduled start for both projects is January 2019.

Work started on five additional proposals in 2018, to be submitted for evaluation in early 2019. CESSDA provided support to its Service Providers in project applications in the INTERREG Danube Transnational Programme calls⁹.

Governance and management

Governance

The governance structure of CESSDA ERIC consists of the General Assembly; the Director; the Service Providers and the Service Providers' Forum, which has an advisory role; and the Scientific Advisory Board.

The General Assembly is the ultimate authority of CESSDA ERIC and consists of the Members of CESSDA ERIC and Observers without voting rights. The Director is the chief executive officer, chief scientific officer and legal representative of CESSDA ERIC.

In June 2018, the new strategy 2018-2022 was adopted by the General Assembly after an extensive consultation process with the Service Providers and the Scientific Advisory Board. Other strategic topics discussed at the November meeting were participation in the European Open Science Cloud, the development of roadmaps for the CESSDA Working Groups, the future development of CESSDA, and risk analysis in relation to coordination roles in large European projects.

The Scientific Advisory Board met in March to discuss CESSDA's scientific and strategic direction. The Service Providers' Forum met twice in 2018, in April and October, and it was decided that its agenda should cover more strategic issues. As of October, these Service Provider Forum meetings are organised on a

lunch-to-lunch basis over two days, which allows for more time for discussion and networking.

The role of the Working Groups was extended: all CESSDA projects are connected to one of these Working Groups: Trust; Training; Technical; Tools & Services. Together with the Main Office, these Working Groups monitored the progress and developments in each strategic area through related projects and their compliance with the CESSDA Strategic Plan 2018-2022.

The CESSDA Working Groups also started preparation of the multi-year roadmaps for each strategic pillar of CESSDA, thus providing guidance for funding and prioritisation of projects in the next years. There were monthly calls and face-to-face meetings of Working Group Leaders and CESSDA's Chief Operations Officer. This improved internal communication and addressed the salient role of the Service Providers as the core of CESSDA.

Governance and management

CESSDA - organigram

Governance and management

Management

Management of the daily operational activities of CESSDA ERIC is done by CESSDA Main Office. Its main activities are project management, communications, finance, IT-platform, acquisition and European networking and lobbying.

In 2018, CESSDA Main Office administratively managed sixteen internal projects (Work Plan Tasks) and four European-funded projects. It supported the preparation of two project applications. In one, CESSDA Main Office was assigned the coordination role¹⁰.

As mentioned above, the new CESSDA Working Group roadmaps were intended to ease the decision making process for new CESSDA Work Plan projects and make sure that they are linked to the CESSDA strategy. A process was worked out for monitoring and evaluating projects.

A Senior Financial Manager was hired to professionalise CESSDA's financial services and to improve its financial monitoring. This replaced previous support received from CESSDA Service Provider NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data and the University of Bergen.

CESSDA Management

* seconded

¹⁰ Both applications were granted funding in 2019. ERIC Forum and SSHOC (incl. coordination of 40+ contract parties and a budget of 14 million Euros).

Governance and management

CESSDA Project Cycle

The IT-platform was further implemented, to accommodate the new CESSDA Data Catalogue and other upcoming tools. The IT-maturity model to check upon the quality and performance of (new) tools was elaborated and expanded with a checklist to support the decision process for accepting, implementing and supporting new IT-based tools and services.

CESSDA Project Deliverables

The Main Office shares its ongoing activities with other research infrastructures, for example via the ERIC Forum, within the Social Sciences and Humanities cluster on strategic issues and cooperation, and at a technical level, the EURISE network was established. It is an umbrella initiative where research infrastructures meet research software engineers, set up as a cooperation between CESSDA, CLARIN and DARIAH.

Looking ahead

CESSDA wants to contribute to the European Open Science Cloud, especially in terms of social science data, according to the FAIR Data principles and with its Service Providers as trusted data repositories. This will help individual researchers, research communities and organisations archive, share and access social research data.

With this in mind, we initiated several internal projects, related to the technical backbone, tools & services, trust and training. We engaged in EU-funded projects and became an active partner in European research infrastructure policy development. We connected with other social science research data infrastructures, such as SHARE, ESS, EVS and GGP, with humanities (CLARIN and DARIAH) and with other disciplinary clusters.

CESSDA also wants to realise full European coverage and strengthen national Service

Providers. We foresee increasing global cooperation, e.g. on standards, thesauri, and developing and implementing tools & services.

We can increase cooperation with US-based ICPSR, and connect with sister organisations in Asia, Australia and Africa. The RDA platform is global and CESSDA co-chairs an Interest Group on Social Sciences Research Data, which means that it could be the perfect avenue for this cooperation.

Several challenges lie ahead, for instance how to increase the willingness to share data. We need to provide researchers with key tools and services for seamless archiving and sharing of data. We must reach out to the researchers, either individually or via their communities and other research organisations. This will be at the heart of our work in the years to come.

Financial statements 2018

CESSDA ERIC

Financial statements

Income statement 2018 (NOK)

Operating income and expenses	Note	2018	2017*
Operating income			
Other operating income	4	16 920 019	12 466 428
Total operating income		16 920 019	12 466 428
Operating expenses			
Payroll expenses	1	6 858 473	3 546 794
Depreciation of fixed assets	2	139 800	35 207
Other operating expenses	1	17 189 225	8 951 883
Total operating expenses		24 187 498	12 533 884
Operating profit		-7 267 479	-67 456
Financial income and expenses			
Other interest income		3 344	14 813
Other financial income		902 158	853 813
Other financial expenses		903 346	19 362
Net financial income and expenses		2 157	849 264
Operating result		-7 265 321	781 808
Annual net result		-7 265 321	781 808
From/ to other equity	5	-7 265 321	781 808
Net brought forward		-7 265 321	781 808

* Applies to the period 01.07.17-31.12.2017

Financial statements

Balance statement 2018 (NOK)

Assets	Note	2018	2017
Tangible fixed assets			
Equipment and other movables	2	164 316	277 963
Total tangible fixed assets		164 316	277 963
Total fixed assets		164 316	277 963
Current assets			
Debtors			
Accounts receivable		-	16 895
Other receivables	1	184 490	407 039
Total debtors		184 490	407 039
Cash and bank deposits			
Cash and bank deposits	3	23 021 769	29 081 990
Net financial income and expenses		23 021 769	29 081 990
Total current assets		23 206 259	29 505 924
Total assets		23 370 575	29 783 887

Financial statements

Balance statement 2018 (NOK)

Equity and liabilities	Note	2018	2017
Retained earnings			
Other equity	5	11 133 105	18 398 426
Total retained earnings		11 133 105	18 398 426
Total equity		11 133 105	18 398 426
Liabilities			
Trade creditors		509 501	481 837
Public duties payable		393 740	555 075
Other short term liabilities	6	11 334 230	10 348 549
Total short term liabilities		12 237 471	11 385 461
Total liabilities		12 237 471	11 385 461
Total equity and liabilities		23 370 575	29 783 887

Bergen, 13 June 2019

Ronald Jacobus Paulus Dekker
Chief Executive Officer

Peter Doorn
Chairman

Bjørn Tore Kjellemp
Vice Chairman

Financial statements

Accounting principles

The accounts have been prepared in accordance with the Norwegian Accounting Act and good accounting practice in Norway. The accounting principles are described below.

Operating income and expenses

Revenues consist mainly of grants and project revenues. Received payments related to activities not carried out at year-end are recognized in the balance sheet as unearned income and classified as other short term debt.

Expenses are recognized in accordance with the matching principle. This means that expenses are recognized in the same period as the related income.

Classification of assets and liabilities

Assets meant for long-term ownership or use are classified as fixed assets. Other assets are classified as current assets. Outstanding receivables to be repaid within one year are classified as current assets. The classification of liabilities is based on analogous criteria.

Fixed assets are valued at acquisition cost. Fixed assets which have a limited economic life shall be depreciated in accordance with a reasonable depreciation schedule. Fixed assets shall be written down to their fair value when a decline in value is not expected to be temporary. The write down shall be reversed when the basis for the write down is no longer present.

Current assets are valued at the lower of acquisition cost and fair value.

Liabilities are appraised at the nominal value on the acquisition date.

Taxes

Since the business is a non-profit organization it is not liable for corporation tax in accordance with the Tax Law § 2-32.

Currency

Monetary assets and liabilities in foreign currencies are valued at the exchange rate at year-end.

Pension

The Norwegian branch has established a defined benefit pension scheme. The pension premium is classified as payroll expenses.

Financial statements

NOTES

Note 1- Payroll expenses, numbers of employees , loans to employees etc

Payroll expenses	2018	2017*
Wages and holiday allowances	5 310 591	2 823 717
Payroll tax	786 035	443 644
Pension premium	567 998	276 519
Other benefits	193 849	2 913
Total	6 858 473	3 546 794
Average number full time equivalent	7,2	6,4
Directors' remuneration	1 274 218	1 015 972
Board fees	0	165 416

As from June 2017, the Board doesn't exist due to the change of organisation form from CESSDA AS to CESSDA ERIC.

The company is obliged to have a pension scheme according to the Norwegian Law of compulsory occupational pension scheme and have established a defined benefit pension scheme which satisfies the requirements.

Audit Fees	2018	2017*
Audit	33 750	23 500
Other services	60 515	9 750
Total	94 265	33 250

Audit costs are exclusive value added tax.

* Applies to the period 01.07.17-31.12.2017

Financial statements

Note 2 - Tangible fixed assets

Assets	2018	2017
Acquisition cost 01.01*	545 596	436 877
Acquisition	26 153	108 719
Acquisition cost 31.12	571 749	545 596
Accumulated depreciation	-407 433	-267 633
Accounted value	164 316	277 963
Depreciation of the year	139 800	35 207
Expected economic life	3-5 years	3-5 years
Deprecation plan	Linear	Linear

* Acquisition cost in 2017 originates from CESSDA AS balance 30.06.2017.

Note 3 - Cash and bank deposits

The bank deposits include NOK 578.285 tax deduction funds.

Deposit	2018	2017
Restricted cash- fixed tax deduction funds	578 285	300 000
Bank deposits in NOK	5 409 734	6 838 377
Bank deposits in EUR	17 033 751	21 943 613
Total	23 021 769	29 081 990

Cessda ERIC has a currency risk associated with the exchange rate developments. Allocated funding to projects are paid in Euros. The bank deposits are in Norwegian Kroner and Euro.

Financial statements

Note 4 - Breakdown of income

Income in the year was derived from the following sources:

Source	2018	2017
Funding from the Norwegian Research Council	7 817 280	3 725 120
Other Grant income	9 102 739	8 741 308
Total	16 920 019	12 466 428

Note 5 - Changes in equity

Equity	2018	2017
Equity 01.01*	18 398 426	0
Reclassification of unearned revenue in CESSDA AS to equity in CESSDA ERIC	0	20 797 985
Change in funds granted, not paid at at 31.12	0	-3 181 340
Result of the year	-7 265 321	781 809
Total equity 31.12	11 133 105	18 398 426

*Equity for 2017 is from CESSDA Balance per 30.06.2017.

Note 6 - Other short term liabilities

Liability	2018	2017
Funds granted to projects, not paid as at 31.12	10 642 202	5 451 513
Funds granted to GESIS - German Service Provider not paid as at 31.12		4 350 497
Other short term liabilities	692 028	546 539
Total other short term liabilities per 31.12	11 334 230	10 348 549

Projects that have been granted funds from CESSDA ERIC, where payments has not taken place at year-end, are classified as other short term liabilities. As of 31 December this amounts to NOK 10.642.202. The change in funds granted, not paid as of 31 December 2018 amounts to NOK 5.190.689, which is included in the year end balance shown above.

BDO AS
O.J. Brochs gate 16A
5006 Bergen

Independent Auditor's Report

To the General Meeting in Cessda Eric

Report on the Audit of the Financial Statements

Opinion

We have audited the financial statements of Cessda Eric.

<p>The financial statements comprise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The balance sheet as at 31 December 2018• The income statement for 2018• Notes to the financial statements, including a summary of significant accounting policies	<p>In our opinion:</p> <p>The accompanying financial statements are prepared in accordance with the law and regulations and give a true and fair view of the financial position of the Company as at 31 December 2018, and its financial performance for the year then ended in accordance with the Norwegian Accounting Act and accounting standards and practices generally accepted in Norway.</p>
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Basis for Opinion

We conducted our audit in accordance with laws, regulations, and auditing standards and practices generally accepted in Norway, including International Standards on Auditing (ISAs). Our responsibilities under those standards are further described in the Auditor's Responsibilities for the Audit of the Financial Statements section of our report. We are independent of the Company as required by laws and regulations, and we have fulfilled our other ethical responsibilities in accordance with these requirements. We believe that the audit evidence we have obtained is sufficient and appropriate to provide a basis for our opinion.

Responsibilities of the Board of Directors and the Managing Director for the Financial Statements

The Board of Directors and the Managing Director (management) are responsible for the preparation and fair presentation of the financial statements in accordance with the Norwegian Accounting Act and accounting standards and practices generally accepted in Norway, and for such internal control as management determines is necessary to enable the preparation of financial statements that are free from material misstatement, whether due to fraud or error.

Financial statements

In preparing the financial statements, management is responsible for assessing the Company's ability to continue as a going concern, disclosing, as applicable, matters related to going concern. The financial statements use the going concern basis of accounting insofar as it is not likely that the enterprise will cease operations.

Auditor's Responsibilities for the Audit of the Financial Statements

Our objectives are to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements as a whole are free from material misstatement, whether due to fraud or error, and to issue an auditor's report that includes our opinion. Reasonable assurance is a high level of assurance, but is not a guarantee that an audit conducted in accordance with ISAs will always detect a material misstatement when it exists. Misstatements can arise from fraud or error and are considered material if, individually or in the aggregate, they could reasonably be expected to influence the economic decisions of users taken on the basis of these financial statements.

For further description of Auditor's Responsibilities for the Audit of the Financial Statements reference is made to:

<https://revisorforeningen.no/revisjonsberetninger>

Report on Other Legal and Regulatory Requirements

Opinion on Registration and Documentation

Based on our audit of the financial statements as described above, and control procedures we have considered necessary in accordance with the International Standard on Assurance Engagements (ISAE) 3000, «Assurance Engagements Other than Audits or Reviews of Historical Financial Information», it is our opinion that management has fulfilled its duty to produce a proper and clearly set out registration and documentation of the company's accounting information in accordance with the law and bookkeeping standards and practices generally accepted in Norway.

BDO AS

Charlotte Bårdsen
State Authorised Public Accountant
(This document is signed electronically)

Bodies of CESSDA

General Assembly

Country	Name
Austria	Matthias Reiter-Pázmándy Bettina Glazer Lars Kaczmirek
Belgium	Laurence Lenoir Aziz Naji
Czech Republic	Kamila Gabrielova Jindrich Krejci
Denmark	Anna Sofie Fink Troels Rasmussen
Finland	Otto Auranen Helena Laaksonen
France	Fabrice Boudjaaba Nicolas Dromel
Germany	Christof Wolf Monika van Ooyen
Greece	John Kallas Dimitra Kondyli
Hungary	Gabor Csirikusz Tamas Rudas
Netherlands	Peter Doorn Joris Voskuilen
Norway	Vigdis Kvalheim Heidi Dybesland
Portugal	Pedro Moura Ferreira Jose Manuel Mendes

Slovakia (observer)	Miloslav Bahna Robert Klobucky
Slovenia	Albin Kralj Janez Stebe
Sweden	Magnus Eriksson Mikael Hjerm
Switzerland	Brian Kleiner Georg Lutz
United Kingdom	Joseph Ellery Matthew Woollard

Service Providers' Forum Representatives (members)

Country	Name
Austria	Lars Kaczmirek Julian Ausserhofer
Belgium	Benjamin Peuch Rolande De Poortere
Czech Republic	Jindrich Krejci Yana Leontiyeva
Denmark	Anna Sofie Fink
Finland	Helena Laaksonen
France	Sebastien Oliveau
Germany	Wolfgang Zenk-Möltgen
Greece	Dimitra Kondyli
Netherlands	Ricarda Braukmann
Norway	Vigdis Kvalheim Dag Kiberg
Portugal	Jose Manuel Mendes Pedro Moura Ferreira

Slovakia	Miloslav Bahna
Slovenia	Janez Stebe Irena Vipavc Brvar
Sweden	Iris Alfredsson Max Petzold
Switzerland	Brian Kleiner Alexandra Stam
United Kingdom	Louse Corti David Hall

Service Providers' Forum Representatives (non-members)

Country	Name
Estonia	Rein Murakas
Hungary	Peter Hegedus
Ireland	John Howard Julia Barrett
Romania	Adrian Dusa
Serbia (member from 2019)	Aleksandra Bradic-Martinovic
Spain	Jesus Bouso Frejo

Members of the Scientific Advisory Board

Name
Myron Gutmann – Chair, Institute of Behavioural Science, University of Boulder, USA
Bernt Aardal – Department of Political Science, University of Oslo, Norway
Denise Lievesley – Cambridge University, UK
Nancy Pedersen – Karolinska Institute, Sweden
Simon Hodson – CODATA
Tomaz Smrekar – National Statistical Office, Slovenia

Trust monitoring status — End of year 2018

Organisation Details				CESSDA Trust Process	CoreTrustSeal Process				
Type	Organisation Name (EN)	Abbreviation	Country	CESSDA Self-Assessment Status	CoreTrustSeal Status	CoreTrustSeal Version	Submitted Date	Approval Date	Renewal Due
Service Provider (SP) Member	Austrian Social Science Data Archive	AUSSDA	Austria	Planned: 2019					
Service Provider (SP) Member	Social Sciences and Humanities Data Archive	SOHDA	Belgium	Planned: 2019					
Service Provider (SP) Member	Czech Social Science Data Archive	CSDA	Czech Republic		Approved	2017-2019	21.12.2017	23.01.2018	23.01.2021
Service Provider (SP) Member	Danish National Archives	DNA	Denmark	Planned: 2019					
Service Provider (SP) Member	Finnish Social Science Data Archive	FSD	Finland		Approved	2017-2019	27.04.2017	18.08.2017	18.08.2020
Service Provider (SP) Member	PROGEDO Research Infrastructure	PROGEDO	France	V1: Submitted 2018					
Service Provider (SP) Member	GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences	GESIS	Germany		Approved	2017-2019	04.08.2017	14.09.2017	14.09.2020
Service Provider (SP) Member	Greek research infrastructure for the social sciences	So.Da.Net	Greece	Planned (resubmit): March 2020					
Service Provider (SP) Member	Tárki Data Archive	TÁRKI	Hungary	tbc					
Service Provider (SP) Member	Data Archiving and Networked Services	DANS	Netherlands		Approved	2017-2019	28.03.2018	28.03.2018	28.03.2021
Service Provider (SP) Member	NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data	NSD	Norway		Approved	2017-2019	23.02.2018	06.03.2018	06.03.2021
Service Provider (SP) Member	Portuguese Social Information Archive	APIS	Portugal	Insufficient Human Resources. 2020 target					
Observer	Slovak Archive of Social Data	SASD	Slovakia	Progress 2019					
Service Provider (SP) Member	Social Science Data Archives	ADP	Slovenia		Approved	2017-2019	23.11.2017	09.01.2018	09.01.2021
Service Provider (SP) Member	Swedish National Data Service	SND	Sweden		Approved	2017-2019	03.02.2018	06.02.2018	06.02.2021
Service Provider (SP) Member	Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences	FORS	Switzerland		Approved	2017-2019	27.02.2018	20.03.2018	20.03.2021
Service Provider (SP) Member	UK Data Service	UKDS	United Kingdom	Planned for 2019					
Partner (SP status in progress)	Data Center Serbia for Social Sciences	DCS	Serbia	Not yet initiated					

CESSDA ERIC

Parkveien 20

5007 Bergen

Norway

+47 401 00 964

cessda@cessda.eu